

On the Nature of Hydrolytic Adsorption.

Part II.

Adsorption of Electrolytes by Barium Sulphate and Liberation of Acids and Alkalis in presence of Neutral Salts.

BY

JNANENDRA NATH MUKHERJEE

AND

JYOTI KANTA BASU.

The general theory has been discussed in a recent paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1, 191, which also contains reference to earlier papers). The present paper deals with experiments on polar precipitates. A very interesting case from the theoretical point of view has been described showing the liberation of either acids or alkalis by the interaction of neutral solutions of potassium sulphate and of barium chloride according as barium or sulphate is in excess. We have also recorded in this paper evidence regarding the displacement of ions in the 'fixed' layer on the surface by those in the solution. The difference between this type of exchange and the displacement of ions in the mobile sheet has been pointed out. From the discussion in this paper it would appear that it is necessary to assume interchanges of ions in the double layer with those in solution to account

for our observations. The difficulties in the way of alternative explanations have also been pointed out.

EXPERIMENTAL.

In this investigation indicators and standards recommended by Clarke and Lubs have been used. The standards have been tested in the laboratory. No filter paper was used as it is well-known that an acid reaction develops when filter papers are brought in contact with neutral electrolytes. The precipitate never came in contact with any surface other than that of the vessels (Jena glass or transparent fused silica) used. Washing was carried by repeated decantations.

(A) *Liberation of Adsorbed Acids and Bases by neutral Potassium Chloride.*

In these experiments 50 c. c. of a normal solution (p_H , 6.4) of barium chloride and of potassium sulphate (p_H 6.4) were added slowly and simultaneously from two burettes (the process taking 10—12 minutes) in a Jena glass bottle containing 25 c. c. of different acids (see Part I, *loc. cit.*, p. 199) regarding precipitation in presence of acids). The contents were kept undisturbed for 24 hours and then the precipitate was washed repeatedly with pure water till the p_H of the wash-water left in contact with it for 24 hours had a value 6.2 to 6.4. The washed precipitate was next left in contact for 24 hours with 50 c. c. of saturated potassium chloride solution (p_H , 6.2—6.4). The results are given in Table I(a). Parallel experiments in which the precipitate obtained in an identical manner was kept in contact with water instead of a solution of potassium chloride did not show a p_H value less than 5.8.

TABLE I (a).

Precipitated in presence of	p_H of the extract with KCl.
10N Hydrochloric acid *	2.2
17N Acetic acid	2.4
8N Phosphoric acid	4.4
4N Citric acid	4.0
4N Tartaric acid	4.2
5N Sulphuric acid	2.2

TABLE I (b)

Precipitated in presence of	left in contact with	p_H of the extract.
N Sodium hydroxide	sat. potassium chloride.	8.0
N. " " "	water	7.2

The same concentration of different acids was next used for comparison. The condition of experiments was identical with that in previous cases except that 50 c. c. of solution of acid were used. The results are given in Table II.

TABLE II.

Precipitated in presence of	p_H value of the KCl extract			
	after 24 hours		after 48 hours	
N-Acetic acid	3.8-4.0		3.8	
N-Monochloroacetic acid	4.2		4.0	
N-Dichloroacetic acid	4.4		4.2	
N-Trichloroacetic acid	4.6		4.2-4.4	
N-Hydrochloric acid	6.0-5.8		4.4	
N-Formic acid	"		5.0	
N-Phosphoric acid	"		5.4	

	with KCl	with water	with KCl	with water
0.98N-Acetic acid	4.0	6.2	3.8	6.3
1.008N-Monochloroacetic acid	4.2	6.2	4.0	6.2
0.98N-Trichloroacetic acid	4.4-4.5	5.8	3.8-4.0	5.2-5.4
N-Hydrochloric acid	5.2-5.4	6.0	4.2	6.0

* The concentrations given are not exact and are meant to convey an idea of the strength of the acid that has been used.

Results of experiments with different concentrations of the same acid are given in Table III.

TABLE III (a).

Precipitated in presence of	p_{H} value of extract.
2.5N. Acetic acid	3.6
0.5N. „	4.0
0.25N. „	4.4
0.125N. „	5.0
0.0625N. „	5.6

TABLE III (b).

Precipitated in presence of	p_{H} value of extract.
0.5N-Sulphuric acid	3.8
0.25N. „	4.0
0.1N. „	4.2-4.4
0.05N. „	4.6

B. *Experiments with carefully washed Barium Sulphate precipitated in the absence of Acids.*

We see from the above that the concentration of the acid liberated in contact with potassium chloride depends on the concentration and nature of the acid used. It was thought desirable to repeat the above experiments with barium sulphate precipitated in the absence of acids from neutral solutions of barium chloride and potassium sulphate.

Equal volumes (generally 50 c. c.) of normal solution of barium chloride and potassium sulphate were mixed

simultaneously from two burettes. The precipitate was washed repeatedly with pure water till the wash-liquid was free from sulphate and chloride. The precipitate was then kept in contact with an acid solution for 48 hours. It was again washed till the filtrate had a p_H equal to that of the water used (6.4). The precipitate was then left in contact with a saturated solution of potassium chloride (p_H , 6.4) for 24 hours and the p_H of the supernatant liquid was determined. It was observed that if the precipitate be washed sufficiently long no acid reaction develops on treatment with potassium chloride showing that the adsorbed acid can be removed more easily from these samples. On the other hand when the washing was not pushed far enough, definite evidence of the liberation of acids on treatment with potassium chloride was obtained as would appear from Table IV.

TABLE IV.

Kept in contact for 48 hours.	Washed free from acid and kept in contact with	p_H after 48 hours.
N-Oxalic acid	saturated potassium chloride (p_H , 6.2)	5.4
N-Oxalic acid	water (p_H , 6.2)	5.8
15N-Sulphuric acid	Saturated pot. chloride.	5.4
15N-Sulphuric acid	water	6.0

The observation that the precipitate does not develop an acid reaction if it is sufficiently washed also shows that the liberation of hydrogen ions is the result of an interaction between adsorbed acids and the neutral salt. In this respect the acidity developed here is different from that observed when hydrated silica or manganese oxides (*cf.* Part I, *loc. cit.*, pp. 211, 215) is treated with a

solution of a neutral salt. Obviously barium sulphate cannot adsorb hydroxyl ions primarily to any perceptible extent as otherwise the acid reaction would be observed, however, long the washing may be continued.

It has been also observed that barium sulphate obtained from barium chloride and sulphuric acid and washed free from acid sets free chloride and sulphate ions in contact with neutral solutions of potassium nitrate and chloride respectively in addition to hydrogen ions. But no barium ions could be detected. We have further observed that small quantities of the adsorbed acids are liberated in contact with pure water.

C. *Development of Alkalinity or Acidity from the double Decomposition of neutral Solutions of Potassium Chloride and Barium Sulphate.*

It has been stated previously (Part I., *loc. cit.*, p.199) that an acid or an alkaline reaction develops on mixing neutral solution of potassium sulphate or barium chloride according as one or the other of the salts is in excess. The theoretical interest of this reaction is considerable.

(i) *Development of Alkalinity when Barium Sulphate is precipitated from Excess of Potassium Sulphate.*

Fifty c. c. of a normal barium chloride (p_H , 6.4) was added to 100 c. c. of normal potassium sulphate (p_H , 6.4) contained in a Jena-glass¹ bottle slowly as before but with constant stirring. The bottle was stoppered and shaken mechanically for 30 minutes and then allowed to stand. After half an hour the p_H value of the

¹ This experiment as also the next one has been repeated in transparent fused silica vessels. No filter paper was used and the solution in these experiments never came in contact with anything other than Jena glass or silica vessels excepting that ordinary pipettes were used. It has been found that during the time for which the solution was in contact with the pipette no change in p_H value can be detected with the indicators.

clear supernatant liquid becomes 8.0. The p_H value exceeds 11.0¹ in two to three days and remains steady afterwards.

(ii) *Development of Acidity with Excess of Barium Chloride.*

Fifty c.c. of normal potassium sulphate was added to 100 c.c. of normal barium chloride as before. The clear supernatant liquid (after 24 hours) does not show any acid reaction but remains neutral (p_H , 6.4). An acid reaction (p_H , 5.0) develops within 3 to 4 weeks. During this time the bottle was kept carefully stoppered in a place free from dust and fumes.

The immediate development of acidity and alkalinity can be demonstrated as follows:—

Two Jena glass test tubes are taken. To one of which are poured 5 drops of phenol red. One c.c. of barium chloride (normal solution) is next added. To the other tube are added 5 drops of methyl red and one c.c. of potassium sulphate (normal solution) and the liquid in both tubes is diluted to 4 c.c. Both the solutions are coloured yellow showing that the p_H , in each case is between 6.0—7.0. These tubes are kept in a holder for comparison. To another Jena glass test tube 2 c.c. of normal barium chloride (p_H , 6.4) 5 drops of methyl red and one c.c. of normal potassium sulphate are added and the solution is diluted to 4 c.c. A pink colour develops within 5 minutes showing on comparison with a phthalate standard a p_H value between 5.2 to 5.4.

To a fourth tube containing 2 c.c. of potassium sulphate and 5 drops of phenol red, 1 c.c. of barium chloride is added and the mixture diluted to 4 c.c. A red

¹ Colour deep blue with thymolphthalein.

colour develops showing a p_H value on comparison with a phosphate standard between 8.0 to 8.2.

If the indicators are added after the precipitation that is, if the precipitation does not take place in the presence of the indicators as in the preceding experiments, a similar acid or alkaline reaction develops. These results have been confirmed by E. M. F. measurements.

Confirmation of the above Observation from E.M.F. Measurements.

Twenty-five c.c. of barium chloride having $p_H = 6.12$ (E. M. F. method—indicator showed p_H , 6.2) are mixed with 12.5 c.c. of potassium sulphate (p_H , 6.0) and 12.5 c.c. of conductivity water (p_H , 6.4) in a conical Jena glass vessel and allowed to stand for 2 hours. The p_H of the upper liquid as determined by E. M. F. method is found to be 4.71. (The colorimetric method is not suitable on account of the presence of suspended particles which makes comparison with the standards difficult. Indicator showed a p_H value of about 5.0 as far as could be determined.) It has also been observed that the liquid above the precipitate gives an acid reaction either with indicator or with hydrogen electrodes so long as there are suspended particles in it. The decrease in acidity noted above is to be referred to a gradual clearing up of the supernatant liquid consequent on settling of suspended particles. It is also easy to understand why no acidity is observed in the upper liquid 24 hours after precipitation (see above) as by this time all the particles have settled and the liquid becomes perfectly clear. The precipitate, however, continues to give an acid reaction with methyl red. The fact that the clear supernatant liquid gradually develops acidity on further prolonged contact with the precipitate is obviously to be attributed

to a gradual diffusion of the acid from layers of liquid surrounding the solid particles. In this connection we would also like to record another interesting observation. When methyl red is added to freshly precipitated barium sulphate which has been prepared from equal volumes of barium chloride and sulphuric acid (normal concentration) and washed till no acid could be detected (with indicators and after 24 hours' contact with water) it takes up a yellow colour which does not change with time (up to 24 hours). An acid reaction (red colour) develops immediately on boiling or on the addition of a neutral solution of potassium chloride after some time. These observations have been repeated and confirmed.

Experiments were also carried out to see whether any acid or alkaline reaction develops when well washed barium sulphate precipitated from equivalent amounts of the reacting neutral salts are kept in contact with a solution of potassium sulphate or barium chloride or a mixture of potassium chloride and sulphate or potassium chloride and barium chloride in the preparation in which they occur in the above instances. No change in p_H was observed (indicators only have been used). It should be mentioned in this connection that when equivalent amounts of the two salts are used for precipitation the liquid either remains neutral (*i. e.*, p_H remains practically unchanged) or develops slight alkalinity (p_H , 7.2—7.4).

Similar development of acidity or alkalinity can be shown if we take the nitrate of barium instead of the chloride and the ammonium or sodium salt in place of potassium sulphate.

(iii) *The Variation in the Alkalinity developed in presence of Excess of Potassium Sulphate with Time.*

We have already seen that the development of acidity or alkalinity takes time. It was, therefore, thought

desirable to follow the change in the alkaline reaction with time somewhat in detail. The stronger alkaline reaction makes it more easy to follow these changes.

Barium sulphate was precipitated with addition of 24 c.c. of normal barium chloride to 25 c.c. of normal potassium sulphate containing 0.01 equivalent of one of the following potassium salts—benzoate, citrate, bromide, salicylate, and of sodium chloride. It was found that a maximum p_H of 11.0 was observed in all cases but after 6 days, the p_H was found to be as follows:—benzoate (10.5), citrate (10.0), bromide (9.5), salicylate (9.0) and sodium chloride (8.0). The upper liquid becomes clear within a few hours after precipitation. Between 3 to 4 weeks each attains a steady p_H of 8.0. A parallel experiment without adding any external salt shows that after a p_H of 11.0 has been attained it diminishes more rapidly to 8.0 within 3 to 4 days. It was also found that with large excess of potassium sulphate there was no change in p_H after the maximum has been attained. The significance of these results will be discussed later.

(iv) Evidence as to the Separation of the Neutral Salt into Acid and Alkali.

Barium sulphate was precipitated with excess of potassium sulphate but the precipitate was washed very thoroughly till free from alkali as shown by the absence of an alkaline reaction after 24 hours. But when the precipitate is shaken with water vigorously the upper liquid shows a p_H of 3.8. Boiling the precipitate with water produces the above acidity very quickly.

When the precipitate is formed from excess of barium chloride, a cloudy suspension is formed on washing and it was not possible to wash it further.

D. *Electro-osmotic Experiments with Precipitated Barium Sulphate.*

From our point of view it is necessary to ascertain the sign of the charge of the precipitate in order to form an idea as to whether the hydrogen ions are coming from the primary or fixed layer of ions, or from the mobile sheet of the double layer. The apparatus is a modification of Brigg's method as used in this laboratory (*cf. Nature*, Dec. 2, 1922.) The results are qualitative. The rate of movement of the bubble is given in cms. per 3 minutes.

(i) *Dependence of the Sign of the charge carried by the Precipitate on the conditions of Precipitation.*

(a) We have already remarked that when precipitated from an excess of barium chloride by adding less than an equivalent amount of potassium sulphate the precipitate forms a colloidal suspension which is difficult to wash. On observing the direction of cataphoresis in a U-tube it is found that the particles are *positively* charged. This observation has been repeated several times and there is no doubt that the particles precipitated from an excess of barium chloride carry a positive charge. If the liquid is decanted as far as possible and pure water is added to the precipitate the suspension that is formed also contains positively charged particles showing that the partial removal of the electrolytes does not change the sign of the charge.

(b) On the other hand the precipitate from an excess of potassium sulphate has no tendency to pass into the colloidal state on washing and the direction of electro-osmosis is with the positive current showing that the liquid in contact with the particles is positively charged and that the particles carry a negative charge. The

precipitate is previously washed free from sulphate before it is used for electro-osmotic experiments.

(c) When the precipitate is formed by mixing equal volumes of normal solutions of potassium sulphate and barium chloride and is washed free from chloride the direction of electro-osmotic flow shows that the particles carry a slight negative charge. We could not observe a positive charge though we repeated the experiments three times.

(d) When precipitated from equal volumes of normal solutions of sulphuric acid and barium chloride and washed free from acid the particles carry a definite positive charge.

(ii) *Variation in the Charge on the Addition of Electrolytes.*

In these experiments the precipitate was obtained from mixing large volumes of hot dilute solutions of potassium sulphate and barium chloride using a very small excess of the sulphate. The precipitate was washed free from sulphate with hot water (70° – 80°). The variations in the charge of the particles in contact with barium chloride and sulphuric acid have been investigated. The data are given below :

Electrolyte.	Concentration.	Rate of movement in cms. per 3 min.s	Sign of charge.
Barium chloride	0 (water)	4.3	Negative
"	0.0002 N	3.9	"
"	0.0004 N	42	Positive
"	0.001 N	10.2	"
	—	—	—
Sulphuric acid	0 (water)	5.5	Negative
"	0.002 N	7.2	"

Discussion.

It will be convenient to discuss the results under two heads as follows.

A. *Generation of Acids and Alkalis by double Decomposition of Neutral Solutions of Potassium Sulphate and Barium Chloride.*

The adsorption of electrolytes by barium sulphate during precipitation is well known (*cf.* Treadwell-Hall, "Analytical Chemistry," Vol. II, 1924, pp. 401-5; Mellor, "Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry," Vol. III, 19, pp. 765-6, where references to literature are given). Hulett and Duschak (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1904, 40, 196) assume the existence of such salts as BaClHSO_4 ; $(\text{BaCl})_2\text{SO}_4$ and $\text{Ba}(\text{HSO}_4)_2$ in the precipitate. Similar salts are also well-known. Whenever explanations based on chemical reactions are put forth the question as to the nature of the solid phase arises.

Are we to regard the solid as a mixture of two or more pure solid phases or as a mixture of solid phases one of which is a solid solution? Further, what is the part played by the solid-liquid interface in these reactions? We have already seen that compounds of barium sulphate with acids are known. Apart from the question of stability of such salts under the conditions of precipitation their formation in minute quantities can explain the development of alkalinity. But so far as we know compounds of barium sulphate with hydroxides of alkali or alkaline earth metals are unknown and it is difficult to account for the generation of acidity on the assumption of the formation of definite chemical compounds.

Besides from the orthodox chemical point of view the relationship between the charge carried by the particles and the chemical reaction which we have observed

is not contemplated. Two alternative explanations may be suggested based respectively (a) on the adsorption of ions and the nature of the electrical double layer surrounding the colloidal particles, and (b) on Donnan's well known conception of equilibrium between ions across membranes. In either case it is assumed that when precipitated from excess of barium chloride the particle has an excess of barium ion adsorbed on the surface, and an excess of sulphate ion when precipitated from excess of sulphate. The particles consequently would carry respectively positive and negative charges. Taking the case when barium chloride is in excess if we assume that the precipitate appears in the form of fine particles forming a sort of membrane and that the 'membrane' structure in places completely encloses the liquid like a sac it is possible to imagine that the liquid enclosed in the sac has a higher concentration of barium chloride than what obtains in the bulk of the liquid outside it. In that event diffusion of barium chloride will set in from inside the sac towards the exterior. On account of the positive charge carried by the membrane the diffusion of the barium ion through it will be slower than that of the chlorine ion with the result that acid will appear outside and alkali inside the sac. Similarly we can account for the alkalinity when the sulphate is in excess. The assumption of a diminution of the rate of diffusion when the membrane has a charge of the same sign is not new. Fischer (*Koll. Zeitsch* 1920, 30, 13) made such an assumption with a view to explain the formation of Liesegang rings on the basis of Bradford's suggestion (*Biochem. J.*, 1916, 10, 167) that the adsorption of constituent ions is in part responsible for the formation of such rings. From the above point of view it would follow that the difference in concentration of barium chloride inside and outside the sac as also the magnitude

of the positive charge will determine the degree of acidity developed. If instead of using barium chloride and potassium sulphate of the same concentration, a higher concentration of barium chloride is used in the precipitation, one would expect that in the initial stages of precipitation the difference in the concentration of barium chloride inside and outside will be increased. Further higher concentrations of barium chloride may also increase the positive charge and thus decrease the rate of diffusion of barium ion still further. But experiments on these lines show the absence of any such effects. There is no material change in the acidity. Moreover, this explanation is based on a number of assumptions of which one cannot be very sure. For instance under the conditions of precipitation it is not very likely that there will be a difference in the concentration of barium chloride to any marked degree. On the other hand a much simpler explanation is possible. From our point of view, we can form the following picture of the double layer. Ordinarily the surface of a pure crystal of barium sulphate consists of barium and sulphate ions spaced in conformity with its crystal structure. When there is an excess of barium chloride present in the solution, some of the barium ions become fixed in close proximity to the sulphate ions and the surface has more barium ions per unit area than otherwise. In this case, there is a probability of a partial displacement of the chlorine ions which are present in the mobile sheet by hydroxyl ions on account of the greater adsorbability of the latter. It is well-known that the effect of hydrogen and hydroxyl ions respectively on negatively and positively charged colloidal surfaces are decidedly greater than that of most other inorganic cations and anions respectively. Some of the chlorine ions of the mobile sheet may be displaced by the hydroxyl ions of water and the displaced chlorine ion

together with the partner hydrogen ion of the hydroxyl ion will maintain the electrical neutrality of the solution. The extent of the replacement will be actually determined by the relative adsorbabilities and concentrations of the two ions. Though the adsorbability of hydroxyl ions is very great its concentration is very small, and only when we have a large development of specific surface and consequently a large solid-liquid interface the effect will be measurable. The sensitiveness of the methods for determining hydrogen ion concentrations makes it relatively easy to observe such effects. We thus see that the amount of acid liberated depends on the following factors—(1) number of barium ions remaining adsorbed at any instant under consideration, (2) relative adsorbability of chlorine and hydroxyl ions, and (3) their relative concentrations. The extent of adsorption of the barium ion depends (*a*) on the number of places on the surface where it can be adsorbed, (*b*) the intensity of its adsorption, and (*c*) its concentration in the solution. The particles are thus coated with molecules of barium hydroxide at places and the liberated acid gradually diffuses away from the surface and on account of the slowness of the process of diffusion and the small amount of acid liberated, the acidity can only be observed at first on adding an indicator to the precipitate itself or when the particles themselves remain suspended in the solution. In time sufficient acid diffuses into the bulk of the liquid to give a measurable effect.

The greater and more rapid development of alkalinity probably indicates either (*i*) a more intense adsorption of sulphate ions on the surface or (*ii*) a greater difference between adsorbabilities of hydrogen and potassium ions than between chlorine and hydrogen ions. Further work is necessary before we can be sure of the case of this difference. We shall see in next section that

hydrogen ions are probably fixed on SO_4^{2-} ion forming HSO_4^- ions.

(B) *Liberation of Adsorbed Acids and Alkalis by Neutral Salt Solutions.*

It has already been stated that compounds between acids and barium sulphate are well-known and that during precipitation, formation of such salts in minute traces has been suggested by several investigators. Formation of complex acids containing barium sulphate cannot account for the positive charge of the surface when the salt is precipitate in the presence of acids or the increase in the negative charge with dilute solution of sulphuric acid observed with barium sulphate precipitated from neutral solutions. That the particles are charged positively shows that we are not dealing with neutral molecules of complex acids present either at the surface or distributed throughout the entire mass but that there is an excess of ions of one kind on the surface. When precipitated in presence of high concentrations of acids the hydrogen ions are primarily adsorbed by the surface and impart a positive charge to it. Strong adsorption of hydrogen ions clearly points to the formation of HSO_4^- ions, the corresponding anion remains mobile in the double layer. On washing the HSO_4^- ions on the surface slowly break down and liberate acids. The stability of the HSO_4^- ions so far as it depends on electrostatic forces can be ascribed to the small diameter of hydrogen ion and the double charge of the SO_4^{2-} ion. On addition of a neutral electrolyte partial replacement of hydrogen ion in the HSO_4^- ion by K^+ ion takes place on account of the high concentration of the latter and KSO_4 ions are formed. The HSO_4^- ions are stable only in presence of high concentrations of acids. The interchange of K^+ and H^+ ions takes place in the fixed

layer of ions and the process will be slower than what would have been the case if we were dealing with an interchange of ions in the solution with those in the mobile layer. Besides the diffusion of the liberated acid from the surface is slow. The gradual increase in acidity of the solution should be ascribed to these factors. On the other hand the electro-osmotic experiments with salts precipitated from neutral solutions and treated subsequently with acids show that the hydrogen ions come from the mobile layer. We have seen that the particles initially carry a negative charge which increases still further at low concentrations of sulphuric acid. Under these conditions more sulphate ions are adsorbed on the surface than the H^+ ions and the latter constitute the mobile layer.

Taking the evidence as a whole we believe that at low concentrations of sulphuric acid the adsorption of sulphate ions predominates over that of hydrogen ions the reverse of which takes place at high concentrations. In concluding the discussion we would point out that the simultaneous measurement of the charge carried by the particles gives a clear idea of the nature of the reaction.